

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING FINE ARTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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The progress of civilization, achievements of science and technology, new relationships in society contribute to the formation of specific connections between art and the modern world. Having become dependent on information technology, art acquired a new level of freedom of expression, and its new position in the cultural development of mankind was determined. All this caused a number of serious changes in the art education system. The current state of society is characterized by inconsistency, which has led to misunderstanding and substitution of aesthetic values. The viewer loses value orientations, the majority of the younger generation does not know and does not strive to learn the classics of national culture. More than ever in modern conditions of scientific and technological progress, the role of science, education, culture and art is increasing.

The problems of education at the beginning of the XXI century seem significant and relevant. The development of modern technologies requires a review and reform of education. It must meet the requirements of modern times, be interesting, of high quality, actively develop the creative potential of schoolchildren, identify gifted children, providing them with assistance in developing and revealing their talent in all areas. Great responsibility for the cultural development and education of the younger generation falls on teachers of secondary schools, since they conduct daily educational work with many millions of children. The teacher is the central figure in the school and the content and quality of the educational process and, to a large extent, the volume and level of knowledge acquired by schoolchildren depend on his professional qualifications. Correctly delivered, well-organized, systematically and interestingly conducted classes in the fine arts play a big role in the spiritual development of students, in the formation of their worldview, in the manifestation and improvement of their creative abilities. A person must deeply feel and appreciate the beauty in nature and art, and be able to work productively and creatively. The search for new approaches to teaching fine arts, their multiplicity, can also manifest itself in a negative form. In the history of art education, attempts have been made repeatedly to rise above realism, there have always been discoverers of new original techniques. But these systems quickly became obsolete, they clearly ran counter to the general objectives of training and education.

And now fine arts lessons, in which secondary school students must learn the basics of realistic depiction, are often, in fact, replaced by labor training or a “skillful hands” club, where they are taught to work with templates and stencils, forgetting about creativity. The student, conscientiously completing the tasks assigned to us, turns into a performer, most often in the future unable to create anything new, his own. Another extreme is also possible, when fine arts lessons turn into simple contemplation of children's creativity, which does not interfere with its spontaneity. The basic principles of teaching methods in fine arts, of course, cannot be considered in isolation from creative tasks. But performing only creative tasks that are not supported by visual literacy will certainly lead to a naive and primitive reflection of reality. To master the means of representation, of course, a creative attitude is required, but to a much greater extent, exercises are required that gradually educate and shape the student's

talents. Fine art should be based on knowledge of laws, historical experience and traditions of visual literacy.

The famous English artist and writer Wu Blake stated: "Genius begins where the rules end" [1]. It is worth paying attention, exactly "where they end", and not before they began. Creativity presupposes the study of all previous experience, and only in this case does the opportunity arise that allows you to create something new, your own. So, what is the role of fine arts lessons in a secondary school - teaching students to correctly look, analyze and depict the world around them or mindlessly copy patterns, teaching them to be accurate and diligent. Fine art, due to its specificity, which consists in a visual reflection of reality, serves as the most effective means of mental, moral, aesthetic, labor and physical education, a means of forming a worldview and should stand on a par with other general educational subjects, occupying its special place and participating in equal rights with them. general development of schoolchildren. Fine arts classes act as an effective means of developing creative imagination and visual memory, spatial concepts, artistic abilities, visual skills, volitional properties, and personality traits of students. It is important to teach students to correctly view, analyze and depict the world around them correctly and in a timely manner, from a very early period of education. Thus, students should be faced with the task of learning to truthfully depict reality through the objective laws of visual literacy. An important task is to maximize the development of all types of feelings in the process of teaching fine arts; the unity and richness of sensations received from the outside world ensure the unity and richness of images of perception.

The aesthetic education of the student, his ability to see and feel the environment in characteristic manifestations is inseparable from practical training. P. P. Chistyakov's attitude "To feel, to know and to be able is complete art" [2] is quite applicable to children's art education. The tendency to feel, know and be able establishes the harmonious development of the student simultaneously along these three channels. Skews in the direction of mere awareness without reinforcement by practical skills are undesirable, just as emasculated training in certain skills is also undesirable. The goal of education should be an aesthetically sensitive student with a well-educated artistic taste, who knows the rules and laws of depiction and is able to carry out in practice artistic and visual tasks of varying complexity in accordance with age.

Mastering rules and laws is necessary to a certain extent and at the right time. With the help of their unconditional logic, many of the children's still discordant concepts are brought into order and organized, and their visual, often chaotic, ideas are also brought into order. In children's drawing, living contemplation plays a dominant role, and the teacher is required to patiently nurture, ripen life's impressions, and their spontaneous, purely childish reflection, until the time comes to support them with logical arguments. It is important that theoretical explanations do not break away from practical drawing and do not get ahead of it. Laws and rules should be linked to the lived experience of those who draw.

Observations of students working under the direct guidance of a competent teacher show that schoolchildren gradually begin not only to look at the surrounding objects, but also to compare them with each other, analyze them from the point of view of form. The idea of the need for a high level of artistic skill as a drawing teacher was promoted by the great Russian artist I. E. Repin at the beginning of the XIX century. He vehemently objected to the opinion,

quite widespread at that time, “that we need mediocre teachers who do not work as artists, but who know how to teach” [3].

Raising a creative person who can do his job with interest, responsibility, love and inspiration is an important task of a modern school. This circumstance requires an appropriate arrangement for teaching fine arts at school. It should not be limited to aesthetic education alone or, on the contrary, only to teaching the basics of visual literacy. The modern understanding of the goals of teaching fine arts includes a wide range of tasks for the development of perception, thinking, acquiring knowledge in the field of art, and mastering practical skills in visual arts. Only highly qualified teacher-artists who work professionally not only in pedagogy, but also in art can successfully solve such problems.

References:

1. School of Fine Arts: textbook. allowance. 5th ed., corrected and expanded. M.: Fine Arts, 2022. Issue 1. 176 p.
2. Repin I.E. Letters to artists and artistic figures. M., 2019. 248 p.
3. Yuldasheva T. O. (2022). Problems of teaching fine arts in secondary schools. Bulletin of the Adygea State University: Philology and art history, (2), 82-91.